

PROBLEMS IN PIANO PERFORMANCE OF VOCAL ART (POP SINGING) STUDENTS AND THEIR SOLUTION

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Abstract: This article analyzes the specific features of teaching piano to student musicians of various specialties, the purpose and task of the "piano" course is based on their application to this contingent of students, the need to activate an individual approach to teaching is based on this. The article defines the concept of "fundamentals of piano culture" in relation to a contingent of students of various specialties (pop singers), developed pedagogical conditions and methods that activate an individual approach to the education of this contingent of musicians, contribute to the effectiveness of achieving the set goals.

Key words: individual approach, basics of culture, specialty, student-musicians, goal-task, pedagogical conditions, methods.

Introduction:

Due to its importance and relevance at the current stage of development of musical pedagogical education, the problem of individual approach in musical education is always in the eyes of scientists and practitioners. An individual approach is one of the most important factors that ensure the effectiveness of the pedagogical process. Various aspects of the problem of personal approach are covered in the works of M. K. Akimov, I. M. Osmolovskaya, B. M. Teplova and others. We can observe this problem in the study of various disciplines - psychophysiology, youth pedagogy, cultural studies. The diversity of psychological and pedagogical research directions requires clarifying the problems related to musical and performing arts - piano pedagogy. This field of culture and pedagogy has great achievements in our country.

Please note that regardless of the student's specialty, piano is one of the compulsory subjects in music educational institutions and higher education, and due to the universal possibilities of this instrument in the development of musical knowledge, it occupies a special place in the training of a musician. Performing culture, musical and creative abilities, understanding the connection between sound and meaning in the transmission of a musical image. It is known that A. Rubinstein considered learning the piano to be the most important means of educating and training a person. He wrote: "*I consider the learning of the piano to be a human interest, and I would even like to force such instruction... into the curriculum of general education.*"¹.

The studied problem is devoted to the method of teaching vocal art (pop singer) students in various musical instruments, including the piano. Lessons for vocal performance students, as well as piano performance students, are conducted individually. Individual lessons are the traditional and, according to many music teachers, the only possible form of

¹ Rubinstein A.G. Box of thoughts: Aphorisms and thoughts. M.; St. Petersburg, 1999. 316 p. (Ser. "Pocket Oracle").

piano lessons. But the history of piano pedagogy proves something else: from the middle of the nineteenth century, group lessons were held, in which many students participated at the same time.

Theoretical research in this field began in the 20s of the last century. It was during this period that non-individual training was called individual group or collective individual. Teachers and researchers have seen various possibilities of individual group lessons and have proposed the following options for their use - for example, conducting only group lessons in a piano class, but maintaining an individual approach to each student, individual and group lessons replacing classes, using group classes only in the initial training period, etc. Despite the insufficient development of the problem at that time and the different approaches of using non-individual lessons in piano teaching, researchers with their help to stimulate interest in learning, optimize the initial stage of musical knowledge acquisition and educational concluded that it is possible to convey information to several students at the same time.

Piano performance lessons for vocal performance (pop singer) students are organized in the form of master classes, open lessons, small group lessons (small group). The main advantage of group training is the ability to use interactive teaching methods, organize various activities that create conditions for solving many educational and creative problems. At the same time, modern practice shows that group training is now used very rarely, mainly in the early stages of teaching piano or seminars and master classes. If the practical experience of teacher-musicians has proven their effectiveness, what makes it difficult to rationally use the potential of non-specialist classes (group and small group) in the educational process. Concepts-individual, small group and group lessons-refer to forms of education, each form having a certain functional potential. Analyzing various definitions of educational forms, we came to the conclusion that several approaches to this concept prevail in didactics.

In our opinion, the functional characteristics of individual, small group and group lessons in teaching piano to vocal singing students are determined by factors that make up the external and internal aspects of the concept of "form of educational organization". This:

- *the number of students in the class;*
- *nature of interaction between all participants;*
- *the level of feedback that appears in the lesson.*

These factors are closely related to each other. Feedback is determined by the nature of the interaction. In turn, the possibility and quality of interaction is determined by the number of participants in the educational process. Due to the influence of the above factors, each lesson has its own characteristics, which are reflected in the following forms:

- ❖ *characteristics of providing educational material;*
- ❖ *the quality of mastering various educational materials, including the formation of skills and competencies;*
- ❖ *control the level of feedback or the quality of assimilation;*
- ❖ *opportunities to use different teaching methods;*
- ❖ *opportunities to manage the educational process;*
- ❖ *level of complexity of organizational activity.*

Individual, small group and group training more or less ensure the functioning of these mechanisms. But the most important criterion for the effectiveness of using different forms of training is to achieve an optimal result with reasonable time costs. In a certain period of the

learning time, the teacher must convey the same information (for example, preliminary theoretical knowledge) to the students. If the teacher repeats this information to each student in an individual lesson, he not only wastes a lot of time, uses it irrationally, but also loses the opportunity to convey knowledge in a more interesting way.

Quantitative composition of students participating in the lesson is an external characteristic of individual, group and small group lessons. The number of students participating in the lesson depends on the specific goals and tasks set by the teacher and the expectations of their achievement in this content: "permanent and temporary groups of students with the same learning abilities and the level of formation of educational abilities and skills unites" [5, p. 266]. Also, the quantitative content depends on the teacher's ability to organize educational activities with such a composition of students. It is not decisive in understanding the essence of lessons (for example, despite the presence of an audience, if the goals set by the teacher concern only one student, the lesson remains individual), the quantitative indicator is mutual is an important component of the secret process and determines its possibilities and possibilities.

We interpret the interaction as a result of joint activity of the participants of the learning process and communication related to this activity. There are several types of interaction: direct, frontal, multilateral, that is, interaction between all participants of the lesson, monologic, dialogic etc.). All of them are based on the mechanism of communication, which means that real communication can only happen in pairs or groups. The larger the group, the less each member of the group can speak (and therefore be heard) in multi-way interaction. This leads to a decrease in the intensity of feedback and makes it difficult for the teacher to determine the level of mastery of the material by students.

Thus, the number of students participating in the lesson and the specific characteristics of the interaction between them are determined by the functional characteristics of individual classes and classes in a small group (small group). Individual lessons characterized by a high level of dialogic interaction and feedback are universal and indispensable in the preparation of a performing class student. But group lessons and small group training also help to significantly optimize the learning process.

Conclusion:

V. Nyrkova, one of the leading piano teachers who worked with a contingent of students of various specialties, noted that piano programs for pianists reflect the specific characteristics of the professional direction of teaching students of various specialties: "the difficulties for theorists are increased, for vocalists it is easiest programs are structured. But for all students, to one degree or another, professionally oriented skills are not required, including reading, listening, sketching, accompaniment, ensemble performance."²

² Nyrkova V.D. Piano course for musicians of various specialties. M.: Muzyka, 1988. 48 p.

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